

Workshop: Laban Movement Analysis in design research: An embodied experience

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Topic Laban Movement Analysis (LMA) is a movement notation system widely used among dancers and choreographers, actors, body-oriented psychotherapists, and more recently in user-experience design. Like music, movement can be observed and notated. The experience of the mover and those observing is a relationship with the environment that can be recorded on a deeper level than reported feedback, an embodied experience (Bartenieff & Lewis, 1980). What is a user or user group's body language? How can designers use this information to better develop spaces that facilitate user needs? This special session workshop proposes using LMA as a tool to observe and record movement in order to analyze the meaning of an experience within a space or with a product.

Purpose The proposed session ties the topics of *ambiguity*, in the uncomfortable interactions often experienced in the pursuit of understanding human behavior, of *poetry*, enhancing the ability to tell a user's story, of *empathy* and *spirituality*, in co-designing by embodying and witnessing the present experience of the user, and overall in informing the study of how the built environment, micro and macro, influence human *well-being*. In celebration of D&E, the session proposes the cross-disciplinary use, from psychology to the performing arts to design, of a movement observation tool applicable to further explorations of human emotions and connections.

Keywords *Laban movement analysis, Movement behavior, Body language, Embodied experience, Ethnography*